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Socio-economic condition of fish fry and fingerling traders in greater Jessore region, Bangladesh

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Abstract

The present study was conducted to assess the livelihood status of fish fry and fingerling traders and socio-economic condition in the greater Jessore, Bangladesh from April 2013 to September 2013. Data were collected through the use of well-structured questionnaire from the selected area. 73% of traders have single family but only 27% have joint family. 45% fish fry and fingerling traders family has four members. 20% family has five members, 14% family has six members, 12% family has three members 9% family has seven to eight members respectively. 92% traders has own bank account but only 7% traders uses their bank account when they trade fry and fingerling. 87% traders have secondary business like rickshaw business, fruit business, cloth business, fish trading etc. Among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders the sanitation facilities are present 100%. It was found that 69% and 31% of fish farmers used semi-pucca and pucca toilet respectively. Among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders 78% of traders have own house but only 22% of trader live in rental house or place. 46% of traders have institutional education that range from primary to higher education and other 54% of traders have no experience in education. In case of illness 58% of traders and trader's family goes to government hospital, 24% uses private clinic, 15% traders are uses local village doctor and another 3% does not get any treatment or not require no treatment. 93% traders have television, 5% house consist radio and another 2% house no instrument for entertainment. Only 10% trader wants their son and grandson engages with this fish fry and fingerling trading profession. The average monthly income of traders in the peak season is 18000 taka and off-peak season the income is less than 7000 taka per month.

Keywords: Socio-economic Condition, Fish Fry, Fish Fingerling traders, Chachra, Entertainment, Next generation employment

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is fortunate in having an extensive water resource in the form of ponds, natural depressions (*haors* and *beels*), huge floodplain, lakes, canals, rivers and estuaries covering an area of 4.56 million ha (DoF 2011). Aquaculture is a significant socio-economic activity, especially for rural communities, contributing to livelihoods, food security and poverty reduction through such mechanisms as income generation, employment, services, diversified farming practices, domestic and international trade and other economic investments serving the sector (NACA/FAO, 2001; Edwards, 2000). Fish fry production and marketing make significant contributions to economic growth, livelihood support and poverty alleviation in the country. So, farmer friendly fish culture is an economic activity of the rural people for augmenting their income, generating employment and ensuring food and nutritional security (Randhir, 1984). In the developing countries like Bangladesh, aquaculture practices have subtle relationships with poverty. Now-a-days, in most of the rural areas in the world especially in the Asian countries, poverty and malnutrition are wide spread among rural people under population pressure. It is estimated that about 70% of the population are living in the rural areas (Edward, 2000). Therefore, poverty alleviation should be considered as an important issue of rural development in which the first requirement is to satisfy the basic needs of the poor. For this, it is essential to have an adequate production of food to meet the basic nutritional requirement of the rural poor. In this respect, aquaculture plays a vital role to supply animal protein as well as to contribute to the food security. Furthermore, it provides employment opportunities and generates foreign currency which has broader impacts on social and economic development (Haque, 2007). Fish fry and fingerling traders make the bridge to the fish fry and fingerling producers and the farmers. They play a vital role in our inland

fishery production. Their social status and socio-economic condition are not so well considering the above fact, this study was conducted to determine the livelihood status and socioeconomic condition of the fish fry traders.

2. Materials and Methods

This study was conducted to assess the livelihood status of the fish fry and fingerling traders as well as socio-economic condition associated with fish production in greater Jessore district for a period of six months from April 2013 to September 2013. 300 respondent of fish fry and fingerling traders were selected for collecting primary data. The study was based on collection of primary and secondary data. The final questionnaire included the questions on the socio-economic characteristics such as age distribution and members of the households, family size, educational status, and occupation, income level of fish fry and fingerling traders, management practices, training received, health facilities, sanitary facilities, housing condition etc. For collection of data, a combination of questionnaire interview, Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) tools such as Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and crosscheck interviews were conducted with fish farmer. Necessary relevant information on the socio- economic condition of farmer was collected from regional offices. All the collected information were accumulated and analyzed by MS-Excel and then presented in textual, tabular and graphical forms to understand the present status of the fish farming technology and the socio-economic condition of the farmer of the studied area.

3. Results

Socio economic condition of fry and fingerling traders

Fry trade is a prospective and profitable sector in fishery business. The farmers who are engaged in this trade were middle class and mostly poor. The educational background of these people was very low. Here the socioeconomic condition of fry and fingerling traders are given below.

Family Status of fish fry and fingerling traders

Most of the fish fry and fingerling traders have single family. 73% of traders have single family but only 27% have joint family.

Fig 1: Present Status of Family of owner of fish trading center.

Family member percentage of fish fry and fingerling traders

Most of the fish fry and fingerling traders have four people in family. 45% fish fry and fingerling traders family has four members. 20% family has five members, 14% family has six members, 12% family has three members 9% family has seven to eight members respectively.

Fig 2: Family member percentage fish fry and fingerling traders.

Bank account holding

276 (92%) traders has own bank account but only 7% traders uses their bank account when they trade fry and fingerling. Other traders use cash or mobile banking like bKash, Mcash, DBBL mobile bank and eCash etc.

Secondary income sources of fish fry and fingerling traders

About 261 (87%) traders have secondary business like rickshaw business, fruit business, cloth business, fish trading etc. They also perform non-government job when they face off season.

Fig 3: Fry and fingerling trading as income source.

Sanitation of fry and fingerling trader's house

Among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders the sanitation facilities are present 100%. They use two types of toilets 1) semi-puccatoilet: made of tin or wood with inadequate drainage disposal and 3) pucca toilet: made of brick with good drainage disposal. It was found that 69% and 31% of fish farmers used semi-pucca and pucca toilet respectively. And 100% fish fry and fingerling traders have tube well facilities.

Fig 4: Sanitation facilities in fish fry and fingerling traders house. *Accommodation*

Among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders 78% of traders have own house but only 22 % of trader live in rental house or place.

Fig 5: Accommodation of fry and fingerling traders.

Education

46% of traders have institutional education that range from primary to higher education and other 54% of traders have no experience in education in Chachra region.

Fig 6: Education of fry and fingerling traders.

Health and Treatment

In Chachra region, among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders in case of illness 58% of traders and trader’s family uses government hospital for health and treatment. And least 24% uses private clinic, 15% traders are uses local village doctor and another 3% does not get any treatment or not require no treatment.

Fig 7: Health and treatment of fish fry and fingerling traders.

Entertainment

There are 300 fish fry and fingerling traders in Chachra region. Among them 93% traders have television, 5% house consist radio and another 2% house no instrument for entertainment in their house. Actually they used to play and watch live game in field or other means of entertainment.

Fig 8: Entertainment facilities of fish fry and fingerling trader’s house.

Next Generation Employment

Among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders, only 10% trader wants their son and grandson engage with this fish fry and fingerling trading profession. But 90% trader want their next generation will involve with other job like doctor, engineer, army officer and government or NGO job.

Fig 9: Next generation employment fish fry and fingerling traders.

Monthly Income of fish fry and fingerling traders

The average monthly income of fish fry and fingerling traders in the peak season is 18000 taka. But in off-peak season the average income is less than 7000 taka per month.

4. Discussion

In the study area, 45% fish fry and fingerling traders family has 4 members. 20% family has 5 members, 14% family has 6 members, 12% family has 3 members 9% family has 7-8 members respectively. In Mymensingh district, most of the fish farmers (45%) were belonging to the family member of 4 to 5 (Ali et al., 2009).

92% traders has own bank account but only 7% traders uses their bank account when they trade fry and fingerling. Other traders use cash or mobile banking like bKash, Mcash, DBBL mobile bank and eCash etc.

About 87% traders have secondary business like rickshaw pulling, fruit business, cloth business, fish trading etc. They also perform non-government job when they face off season which was more or less similar to the findings of Bashar, M.A. (1995).

It was found that 69% and 31% of fish farmers used semi-pucca and pucca toilet respectively. Where Ali et al., (2009) in his study found that 62.5% of the farmers had semi-pucca, 25% had kancha and 12.5% had pucca toilet. The data is relevant with the present study.

Kabir et al., (2012) also found that 100% traders’ household used tube-well water for drinking purposes, among them 40%

had their own tube-well, 50% used shared tube-well and remaining 10% used neighbors tube-well. The data is relevant with the present study.

From the present survey, Among 300 fish fry and fingerling traders 78% of traders have own house but only 22% of trader live in rental house or place. On the other hand Ali *et al.* (2008) found that 54% fish farmer had tin shed, 26% had half building, 14% had building and only 6% had katcha house.

About 46% of traders have institutional education that range from primary to higher education and other 54% of traders have no experience in education in Chachra region. Khan, M.S. (1986) stated that the level of education is a factor affecting utilization of pond for fish farming. The reported literacy rate was found higher than the national adult literacy level of 65% (BBS, 2002). Zaman *et al.*, (2006) found that 23.3% fish farmers and traders were illiterate whereas 14.4%, 8.9% and 6.7% were educated up to primary, secondary and higher secondary or above level respectively. The data is relevant with the present study.

In case of illness 58% of traders and trader's family uses government hospital, least 24% uses private clinic, 15% traders are uses local village doctor and another 3% does not get any treatment. Ali *et al.*, (2008) found that 46% of the farmers received health service from village doctors, 18% from upazila health complex, 14% from district hospital and 20% from MBBS doctors.

Among them 93% traders have television, 5% house consist radio and another 2% house no instrument for entertainment in their house.

In the present study it show only 10% trader wants their son and grandson engage with this fish fry and fingerling trading profession. But 90% trader want their next generation will involve with other job like doctor, engineer, army officer and government or NGO job.

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